

cm; and whole sample, 0-15 cm. Soil analytical data are presented in Table 1.

Eight fertilizer levels were tested (Table 2) in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

All the P and K, and 1/3 the N were applied basally after final land preparation. The remaining N was topdressed, 1/3 at 25 d after transplanting (DT) and 1/3 at 45 DT. Purbachi rice seedlings (35 d old) were transplanted at 25- × 15-cm spacing. Application of 120 kg N, 34 kg K/ha gave the highest yield. No significant yield differences were found when K was applied at 17-51 kg/ha with 80-120 kg N/ha (Table 2). The relatively low effect of K on grain yield may be attributed to the increased K content of the surface silts. ■

Table 2. Yield parameters of boro rice planted on flash-flooded fields and fertilized with N and K, Hathazari, Bangladesh, Jan-Apr 1988.

Treatment (kg NPK/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain Yield (t/ha)
0-0-0	186.30	45.21	21.15	1.4
0-28-34	213.97	51.09	22.55	2.1
40-28-34	244.89	63.12	23.03	3.0
80-28-0	266.62	72.12	23.09	3.7
80-28-17	276.07	77.67	23.32	4.1
80-28-34	277.42	77.84	23.44	4.1
80-28-51	274.72	77.14	23.60	4.2
120-28-34	308.47	76.67	24.76	4.4
CV (%)	12.44	11.44	2.05	7.3
LSD (0.01)	63.74	15.49	0.50	0.5

^aFrom urea, triple superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Response of rice to *Azospirillum brasilense* and organic manures on organic- and chemical-fertilized farms in India

R. Subramanian and M. Rangarajan, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

Field trials were conducted in lowland rice culture during Sep 1988-Feb 1989 on two farms in Pondicherry, India, using White Ponni rice variety. One farm (Gloria Land) had adopted organic farming 10 yr before. The other farm (farmer's field) had for several years used only chemical fertilizers.

The field trials were laid out in a randomized block design with nine treatments and four replications. The control plots on the two farms differed; the farmer's field plot received 100:50:50 kg NPK/ha. Other treatments included farmyard manure (12.5 t/ha), leaves of *Azadirachta indica* (6.25 t/ha), and cow dung slurry (5.0 t/ha) alone and in combination with *A. brasilense* (seed, seedling, and soil application).

Grain yield in Gloria Land increased with some treatments (see table). The

Response of White Ponni rice grown in organically and chemically fertilized fields. ^a Pondicherry, India Sep 1988-Feb 1989.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	Gloria Land	Farmer's field	Gloria Land	Farmer's field
No addition	5.7	-	8.1	-
100 N-50 P-50 N	-	5.1	-	7.4
Farmyard manure (FYM)	5.9 (3.15)	4.4	8.8 (7.5)	6.9
Green leaf manure (GLM)	6.7 (17.7)	4.1	9.9 (21.9)	6.5
Cow dung slurry (CS)	6.1 (6.1)	4.0	8.7 (7.1)	6.4
<i>Azospirillum</i>	5.9 (2.6)	4.1	7.5	6.5
FYM + <i>Azospirillum</i>	6.2 (9.1)	5.1 (1.2)	8.8 (8.2)	7.0
GLM + <i>Azospirillum</i>	6.8 (18.2)	4.9	9.8 (19.8)	6.9
CS + <i>Azospirillum</i>	6.2 (8.6)	4.9	9.8 (20.5)	6.4
FYM + GLM + CS + <i>Azospirillum</i>	6.8 (19.2)	5.7 (13.3)	10.4 (28.3)	7.6 (3.7)
LSD	0.4	0.2	1.7	0.5

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentage increase.

effect on yield of different organic manures with or without *Azospirillum brasilense* varied, depending upon the N content of the organic manures. In the farmer's field, N fertilizer yielded less than the control plot of Gloria Land. Combined application of organic manures plus *A. brasilense* gave significantly

higher grain yield than N fertilizer alone.

In Gloria Land, where organic manures had been applied for several years, *Azospirillum* application did not have a significant effect. In the farmer's field, *Azospirillum* application increased grain yield significantly. Straw yields followed a similar trend. ■

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.